
INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL EFFICIENCY AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE: A STUDY OF LISTED ICT COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract *This study ascertained the effect of intellectual capital efficiency on financial performance of listed ICT companies in Nigeria, using structural capital efficiency and innovation capital efficiency to measure the independent variable (intellectual capital), while return on assets was used for financial performance. Ex post facto research design was adopted for the study. Panel least square regression was employed to test the hypotheses. The result indicates that structural capital efficiency has a negative and significant effect on return on assets of listed ICT companies in Nigeria. On the other hand, the study found that innovation capital efficiency has a positive and insignificant effect on return on assets of listed ICT companies in Nigeria. This study therefore recommended among others that companies should capitalize more on its innovation capital to sufficiently improve its ROA, which is a measure of corporate financial performance.*

Keywords: *Structural capital efficiency, Innovation capital efficiency and financial performance*

Introduction

The transition from an industrial economy, focused on physical assets like factories, machinery, and equipment, to a knowledge-based economy has redefined the sources of wealth and competitive advantage for modern businesses (Sylvanus, Okoye, Amahalu & Mbonu, (2024). The emphasis has shifted to intellectual capital, which includes expertise, creativity, skills, and experience (Inyada, 2018; Ekwe, 2012). This shift has profoundly impacted production systems, now driven by technology and knowledge, with intellectual capital becoming a crucial resource for organizational success (Hojatollah & Alireza, 2013).

Most economies today are being driven by innovation, technology and information, which was not the case few decades back when machines were the drivers of the economy. These two eras have been differentiated by their mode of operations and resources (Ese, Akpan, Affiong and Mfon, 2024). The value of firms in the machine era was determined by plants, machinery, materials and equipment,

while knowledge, ability, skills, experience and employee attitudes form the current era. In the current era, intellectual capital is a significant asset against the belief of the previous eras that land, labour and capital are the main determinants of economic activities (Ahangar, 2011).

Intellectual capital (IC) is an intangible asset essential in today's knowledge-driven economy, significantly influencing corporate performance. Researchers like Rastogi (2000) and Lev and Radhakrishnan (2003) argue that traditional measures fail to capture IC's true value, as it is both invisible and intangible. IC, comprising Human Capital Efficiency, Structural Capital Efficiency, and Capital Employed Efficiency, fosters innovation, competitive advantage, and value creation (Efenyumi, Okoye & Nwoye, 2022).

In the knowledge economy, intangible assets are recognized as vital for the survival and performance of organizations, particularly in service industries like finance and pharmaceuticals, where intellectual capital is central to revenue generation (Firer & William, 2003). Despite this shift, traditional accounting practices continue to prioritize physical assets, often neglecting the value of intellectual capital in financial statements. This oversight deprives management of critical information needed for decision-making, particularly concerning human resources, which can ultimately impact financial performance (Amahalu, Ezechukwu & Okudo, 2022; Amahalu, Okudo, Okafor & Onyeka, 2023).

Some firm's still post higher and better financial performance figures and better services than the former. Also, at the Nigerian Exchange Group, the rate of revenue generated by these new generation banks as well as their market capitalization has steadily increased and remained superior to those of the old generation banks because the new generation banks invest more in their human asset and provide better incentives that will motivate them to work harder and put in their best (Ekwe, 2014).

This study therefore, ascertains the effect of intellectual capital efficiency on firm performance of listed ICT companies in Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Ascertain the effect of structural capital efficiency on financial performance of listed ICT companies in Nigeria.
2. Determine the effect of innovation capital efficiency on financial performance of listed ICT companies in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Intellectual Capital

Intellectual capital is an intangible asset that increases the quality of accounting information in a company (Mahmoud et al., 2020). The International Accounting Standard (IAS) 38 describes the recognition and disclosures of information on intangible assets (Mahmoud et al., 2020). It states that intangible assets should be recognized only if it is probable that the future economic benefits attributable to the assets will flow to the company, and the cost of the asset can be measured reliably.

This provision is maintained whether such assets are obtained externally or created internally, and conformity with this provision helps to provide information which will advance the quality of intangible assets (Mahmoud et al., 2020). Undeniably, intellectual capital has no generally accepted meaning (Muhammad, 2010); nevertheless, scholars have proven that it comprises of knowledge, experience, brain power of employees, systems, processes, procedures and relations.

Another variant of intellectual capital efficiency is structural capital efficiency which is the ratio of structural capital to VA i.e. $\frac{SC}{VA}$, where SC is the difference between VA and HC i.e. $SC = VA - HC$ (Ulum et al., 2017). Relational capital efficiency is also a variant of intellectual capital efficiency which is the ratio of relational capital to VA i.e. $\frac{RC}{VA}$, where RC = relational capital (Ulum et al., 2017).

Relational capital is usually captured with marketing, selling and advertising costs (Xu & Zhang, 2021). Mavridis (2004) reported that VAIC is more precisely called a measure of intellectual capital performance as it does not measure intellectual capital efficiency but intellectual capital management. The idea is that a company tends to perform excellently with a good and well-maintained intellectual capital (Ulum et al., 2017).

Structural capital as organizational capital denotes the intangible assets in the structure of the company in addition to technological infrastructure that advances the knowledge flow for guaranteeing corporate productivity (Yousaf, 2022). It is the intangible asset which forms the infrastructure needed by human resources to creating value, provides the structure and technical tools for knowledge drift and corporate advancements. It comprises organizational resources like management measures, approaches, innovations, frameworks, processes, information, designs, plans, databases, structures, infrastructural assets, intellectual property rights, research and development expenditures, software, hardware, corporate culture, functions, and strategies that guarantee competitive advantage for the company (Gupta et al., 2020). This type of intellectual capital assists the workforces of the company to boost their on-the-job performance which in turn improves corporate performance.

High quality links are the critical elements of relational capital and the central belief is to be able to form such organizational culture that could help achieve corporate objectives. In a knowledge-based economy, innovation is a vital factor for ensuring corporate competitive advantage. Similarly, economic growth in advanced nations largely confirms this argument that innovation guarantees competitive advantage than investment (Kuzey et al., 2022). Therefore, innovation capital advances from the conjoint influences of human capital and structural capital, as it can be made only with the blend of efficient employee, rational guidelines, culture and systems.

Financial Performance

In practice, professionals see performance appraisal as a fundamental measure of managerial efficiency which largely defines firm survival (Ali et al., 2020). As market competition rises globally, corporations are concerned with increasing their financial buoyancies in order to maintain good competitive stand, fascinate foreign direct investments and maintain viable economic and financial improvement (Ohidoa & Kolade, 2024). Financial performance is frequently employed in determining the stability of the corporation which is the critical concern of stakeholders as well as top management team of the organization. Keter et al. (2024) documented that financial performance functions as a pointer to investors on corporate ability to excellently use its resources to meeting its financial obligations, settle the financial interests of stakeholders, and create incomes for the corporation.

Consequently, corporations logically and judiciously measure performance in quantitative terms to identify areas of advancement; appraise the productivity of corporate policies, take informed decisions, set accountability measures for corporate undertakings, and set standard to surpass competitors (Al-Hashimi et al., 2023). The operationalization of financial performance is a fundamental undertaking to corporations as different organizations employ different measures that suit the achievement of set goal and objectives (Ali et al., 2020). Abubakar et al. (2021) and Ali et al. (2020) noted that there are two approaches of measuring financial performance. It comprises measures such as market value and share price. Debatably, Tobin Q and market value added (MVA) can be employed as measures of financial performance under both approaches (Galant & Cadez, 2017); consequently, both approaches are commonly recognized as measures of financial performance (Ohidoa & Kolade, 2024).

Empirical studies

Ese, Akpan, Affiong and Mfon (2024) examined the effect of intellectual capital on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria from 2007 to 2021. A sample of six deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group, were selected. The study employed a descriptive statistic and regression analysis was used to test the two hypotheses. The result shows that relational capital efficiency has no significant effect on the performance of deposit banks in Nigeria. Also, the result indicated that human capital efficiency has significant effect on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Sylvanus, Okoye, Amahalu, & Mbonu (2024) analyzed the effect of intellectual capital efficiency on firm performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria from 2012 to 2018. Data for the study were extracted from annual reports and accounts of selected companies. The study applied the Value Added Intellectual Coefficient (VAIC) model. Three research hypotheses were formulated for the study. Both descriptive statistics and multiple panel regression techniques for quoted sampled

firms analyzed with the aid of E-Views version 9. The study revealed that Intellectual capital (IC) has a positive significant effect on ROCE and ROA, and there was no significance found for earnings per share. Blessed (2022) determined the effect of intellectual capital on performance of listed non-finance firms on the Nigerian Exchange Group market. This study includes structural capital efficiency, capital employed efficiency, human capital efficiency and value-added intellectual capital coefficient. However, it was concluded that structural capital efficiency, capital employed efficiency and value-added intellectual coefficient significantly improve firm performance. Hossain, Salam, Reza and Hasan (2022) ascertained the effect of intellectual capital and its elements (e.g., human capital, structural capital and capital employed) on the profitability, market value, and productivity of all 30 publicly traded banks listed on the Dhaka Stock Exchange in Bangladesh. The findings of the study suggest that the listed banks in Bangladesh failed to exploit intellectual capital well enough to gain a competitive advantage. Rehman et al. (2022) determined the effect of intellectual capital efficiency on bank performance of one hundred and twenty-nine (129) Islamic banks in twenty-nine (29) countries in the Middle East, South-Asia, and South-East Asia from 2008 to 2017. Data were extracted and analyzed using the 2SYS-Generalised Method of Moment (GMM) regression technique. The study found a positive and significant relationship between human capital efficiency and bank performance. Also, the study revealed a positive and significant relationship between structural capital efficiency and bank performance (proxied with ROA and TQ) but a negative and significant connection with ROE. Lawal et al. (2019) determined the association between intellectual capital efficiency and profitability of six (6) quoted health care corporations in Nigeria for the period of ten (10) years from 2008 to 2017. The data collected were analyzed using multiple regression technique and found a positive and significant association between structural capital efficiency and profitability. The study showed human capital efficiency, relational capital efficiency has no significant effect on profitability in Nigeria. Girma (2017) studied the effect of intellectual capital efficiency on financial performances of ten (10) quoted commercial banks in Ethiopia for the period of six (6) years from 2009 to 2014. Using multiple regression technique, the study found a positive and significant connection between VAIC and financial performance.

Methodology

This study is motivated by the positivist research philosophy and anchored on the deductive research strategy, which includes the numerical measurement of variables. The study used an *ex post facto* research design because the study tends to investigate how past actions can predict certain causes i.e how historical data from annual reports can be used to predict future certain causes and variations in financial performance as occasioned by intellectual capital components. The study is country-specific, and the data for the study was collected from the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as well as the

corporate annual reports of companies under review for the respective years. The rationale for using the secondary data was due to the research design adopted for the study. The data sourced covered a period of seven (7) years from 2017 to 2023.

Population of the study

The population of the study comprised all the eight (8) listed ICT companies listed on the NGX as at 31st December, 2023. The ICT sector was considered as technology is a networking infrastructure that requires skills, experience, and is highly intellectual capital intensive.

Sample and Sampling Technique

Using the census sampling technique, the 8 listed ICT companies were taken as sample due to the smallness of the population of the study.

Model specification

This study adapted the model functional relationship between intellectual capital efficiency and corporate financial performance of Xu et al. (2022) as follows:

$$ROA = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CEE_{i,t} + \beta_2 HCE_{i,t} + \beta_3 SCE_{i,t} + \beta_4 RCE_{i,t} + \beta_5 INCE_{i,t} + \beta_6 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_7 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_8 GDP_{i,t} + \beta_9 CPI_{i,t} + \sum YEAR + \varepsilon_{i,t} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$ROE = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CEE_{i,t} + \beta_2 HCE_{i,t} + \beta_3 SCE_{i,t} + \beta_4 RCE_{i,t} + \beta_5 INCE_{i,t} + \beta_6 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_7 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_8 GDP_{i,t} + \beta_9 CPI_{i,t} + \sum YEAR + \varepsilon_{i,t} \dots \dots \dots (ii)$$

Where i and t represent firm and year respectively;

β represents the presumed parameter; and

ε represents the error term.

$$\text{Corporate Financial Performance} = f(\text{Intellectual Capital Efficiency}) \dots \dots \dots (iii)$$

$$\text{Corporate Financial Performance} = f(\text{Modified Value Added Intellectual Coefficient - MVAIC}) (iv)$$

Flowing from the functional model, MVAIC was decomposed into

Human capital efficiency (HCE),

Structural capital efficiency (SCE),

Relational capital efficiency (RCE), and

Innovation capital efficiency (InCE).

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SCE_{it} + \beta_2 ICE_{it} + \beta_5 FSZ_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (v)$$

Where:

ROA = Return on Asset;

SCE = Structural Capital Efficiency;

ICE = Innovation Capital Efficiency;

FSZ = Firm Size;

ε = The Stochastic Error Term;

i = Company; t = Period Covered;

β_0 = Intercept;

β_1, β_2 = Parameter Estimates;

Method of Data Analysis

The researcher employed the descriptive and inferential statistics to evaluate the data assembled for the study. The descriptive statistics includes the mean, median, minimum, maximum, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis and Jarque-Bera statistics. Also, Panel least squares regression analysis was used as an inferential statistic to test the hypotheses of the study.

4.1 Data Analysis

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	ROA	SCE	ICE	FSZ
Mean	2.367594	-0.01267	0.170389	9.542423
Median	0.148392	-0.00014	0.000000	9.830662
Maximum	78.72099	0.768319	1.961909	12.18343
Minimum	-0.60117	-1.02232	-0.52876	0.000000
Std. Dev.	11.82155	0.305241	0.364100	1.956968
Skewness	5.596158	-0.64142	2.360774	-4.13064
Kurtosis	34.40858	6.208795	12.03769	21.08678
Jarque-Bera	2691.123	27.86475	242.6031	922.5543
Probability	0.000000	0.000001	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	131.5717	-0.70941	9.541777	534.3757
Sum Sq.				
Dev.	7686.193	4.474922	7.291284	210.6349
Observations	56	56	56	56

Source: Researcher's Compilation (2025)

The above table shows that ROA has mean value of 2.367594 with standard deviation (SD) values of 11.82155. The maximum value of ROA is 78.72099 while the minimum values are -0.601174. The Jarque-Bera (J-B) value is 2691.123 with associated probability values of 0.000000 respectively show that the value for corporate financial performance is not normally distributed. The mean value of the explanatory variables (SCE, and ICE) is -0.01267 and 0.170389; their maximum values are 0.768319 and 1.961909 while their minimum values are --1.022320, and -0.528756. The J-B values associated with the explanatory variables are 27.86475 and 242.6031 with associated probability values of 0.000000. In relation to the control variable, FSZ has mean and median values of 9.542423 and 9.830662 respectively. It has maximum and minimum values of 12.18343 and 0.000000; the

standard value of 1.956968, a J-B value of 922.5543 with an associated probability value of 0.000000 which suggests that size of the firm has a fundamental influence on financial performance.

Correlation Analysis

The correlation analysis is an instrument which helps in determining the level of association between variables. It is also a prima facie test for multicollinearity which states whether the relationship between the variables is strong or weak based on the closeness of the correlation coefficient (r) to 1.

Table 2: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

Variable	Coefficient Variance	Uncentered VIF	Centered VIF
C	2.968282	2.562580	NA
SCE	0.137726	4.755788	4.711915
ICE	1.555239	2.132731	1.743880
FSZ	0.127719	1.042931	4.137154

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

The test of multi-collinearity was carried out using Breuch-Pagan-Godfrey test. The test reveals that the centered VIF of the respective regressors are not up to the rule of the tomb of 10. This denotes the lack of multicollinearity in the model.

Table 3: Panel Estimation Output

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob
C	0.190949	0.209625	0.910908	0.3674
SCE	-0.05054	0.010455	-4.8343	0.0000
ICE	0.001041	0.051703	0.020133	0.984
FSZ	0.012446	0.002991	4.160558	0.0001

Effects Specification

Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)

Period random

Idiosyncratic random

Weighted Statistics

R-squared	0.89696	Mean dependent var	2.975007
Adjusted R-squared	0.868205	S.D. dependent var	6.125242
S.E. of regression	2.044219	Sum squared resid	179.6897

F-statistic	31.19287	Durbin-Watson stat	1.951019
Prob(F-statistic)	0.00000		
Unweighted Statistics			
R-squared	0.961547	Mean dependent var	2.349494
Sum squared resid	295.558	Durbin-Watson stat	2.52912

Source: Researcher's Compilation (2025)

Flowing from the table 3, the panel regression result showed the effect between intellectual capital efficiency and financial performance of listed ICT companies in Nigeria. Intellectual capital efficiency was decomposed into SCE, and ICE while financial performance was measured using ROA. The R-Squared value of ROA is 0.896960 (89%) while the adjusted R-Squared values are 0.868205 (86%). This indicates that the explanatory variables explained 86% systemic variation. The F-stat coefficient of ROA is 31.19287 with associated probability value of 0.000000. It shows that there is a significant linear effect between ROA and the explanatory variables. The Durbin-Watson (DW) statistics of ROA is 1.951019, which revealed the absence of autocorrelation in the models as the coefficients are relative to the bench mark of 2.

The coefficient and probability values of the explanatory variables (SCE, and ICE) are presented as follows: -0.050543 (0.0000), and 0.001041 (0.9840). The result reveals that SCE was found to have a negative and significant relationship with ROA. ICE has a positive and insignificant effect with ROA. In relation to the control variable, FSZ has a positive and significant effect with ROA.

Discussion of Findings

SCE has a negative and significant effect with ROA. The result does not align with human capital theory as well as the apriori expectation ($\beta_1 > 0$) which implies that the competitive intelligence, information systems, patents, policies, and processes resulting from the products or systems the corporations have created over time have a significant and adverse influence on ROA. This finding largely support the finding of Ozkan et al. (2017) but inconsistent with Lawal et al. (2019). ICE has a positive and insignificant effect with ROA. The positive and significant association aligns with human capital theory as well as the apriori expectation ($\beta_3 > 0$) which implies that the companies under investigation prioritise expenditures on R&D (ICE) so as to have competitive advantage, resolve corporate issues and improve market value (corporate financial performance). The result supports the finding of Xu et al. (2022).

Conclusion

This study ascertained the effect of intellectual capital efficiency on financial performance of listed ICT companies in Nigeria. Structural capital efficiency and innovation capital efficiency were used to measure the independent variable (intellectual capital), while return on assets was used for financial performance. Panel least square regression was employed to test the hypotheses. The result indicates that structural capital efficiency has a negative and significant effect on return on assets of listed ICT companies in Nigeria. On the other hand, the study found that innovation capital efficiency has a positive and insignificant effect on return on assets of listed ICT companies in Nigeria. In general, intellectual capital has a significant effect of financial performance of ICT companies in Nigeria.

Recommendations

This study thus puts forward the following policy recommendations that:

1. Companies should make maximum use of its structural capital to positively or favourably advance its performance, become a leader in the competitive market, as well as maintain a cost leadership position in the market.
2. Companies should capitalize more on its innovation capital to sufficiently improve its ROA, which is a measure of corporate financial performance.

References

- Abubakar, B. A., Yahaya, O. A., & Nma, A. M. (2021). Board features and financial performance of Nigerian banks. *International Journal of Finance & Banking Studies*, 10(1), 56 - 78.
- Al-Hashimi, Y. N., Al-Toobi, J. S., & Ahmed, E. R. (2023). The influence of corporate governance on firm performance during the Covid-19 pandemic. *Financial Markets, Institutions and Risks*, 7(1), 109 - 122. [http://doi.org/10.21272/fmir.7\(1\).109-122.2023](http://doi.org/10.21272/fmir.7(1).109-122.2023)
- Ali, S. A., Yassin, M., & AbuRaya, R. (2020). The impact of firm characteristics on corporate financial performance in emerging markets: Evidence from Egypt. *International Journal of Customer Relationship Marketing and Management Volume*, 11(4), 70 - 89. DOI: 10.4018/IJCRMM.2020100105
- Ahangar, G. (2011). The relationship between intellectual capital and financial performance: An empirical investigation in an Iranian company. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(1), 88-95.

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Official Journal of America Serial Publication

- Amahalu, N.N., Ezechukwu, B.O., & Okudo, C.L. (2022). Intellectual capital and market value added of listed insurance companies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Science Academic Research*, 03(10), 4528-4533.
- Amahalu, N.N., Okudo, C.L., Okafor, O.O., & Onyeka, C.M. (2023). Effect of human resource cost on profitability of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Commerce and Management Studies (IJRCMS)* 5(3), 60-76.
- Blessed, A. D. (2022). Intellectual capital performance of non-finance firms in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Innovation Research*, 10(1), 1-17.
- Dalton, D. R., Daily, C. M., Ellstrand, A. E., & Johnson, J. L. (1998). Meta-analytic reviews of board composition, leadership structure, and financial performance. *Strategic Management Journal*, 19, 269 - 290.
- Efenyumi, P.M.E., Okoye, E.I. & Nwoye, U.J. (2022). Empirical Evaluation of Effects of Intellectual Capital Efficiency on Firm's Value in Some Selected Listed Firms on Nigerian Exchange Group, *International Journal of Research in Social Science and Humanities (IJRSS)*, 3(6), 16 – 37.
- Ese B. N., Akpan, D. C., Affiong, O. and Mfon, U. E. (2024). Intellectual Capital and Financial Performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*. 10(12). 2504-8856 P-ISSN 2695-2211 12 2024. www.iiardjournals.org Online Version
- Firer, S. & Williams, M. (2003). Intellectual Capital and Traditional measures of Corporate Performance. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*. Vol.4 No.3 Pp. 48-60
- Firas, N., Mardan, N, C-A., & Abdullah, Z. (2021). Intellectual capital as a moderating effect between corporate governance, and firm performance: A conceptual review. *Universal Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 9(6), 1470 - 1477. DOI: 10.13189/ujaf.2021.090623.
- Galant, A., & Cadez, S. (2017). Corporate social responsibility and financial performance relationship: A review of measurement approaches. *Economic Research Ekonomiska Istraživanja*, 30(1), 676 – 693. DOI: 10.1080/1331677X.2017.1313122

Michigan International Journal of Corporate Finance and Accounting

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Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MIJCFA>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

- Girma, B. (2017). Intellectual capital efficiency and its impact on financial performances of Ethiopian commercial banks. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 8(8), 17 – 31. www.iiste.org
- Gupta, K., Goel, S., & Bhatia, P. (2020). Intellectual capital and profitability: Evidence from Indian pharmaceutical sector. *Vision*, 24, 204 – 216. doi: 10.1177/0972262920914108
- Hojatollah S. & Alireza H. (2013). The review on impact of intellectual capital on financial performance of investment companies accepted in Tehran stock exchange organization (TSEO). *European online journal of natural and social sciences*, 2 (3).
- Hossain, M. K., Salam, M. A., Reza, M. M., & Hasan, M. T. (2022). Impact of intellectual capital on profitability, market value, and productivity of the listed banks: Evidence from Bangladesh. *International Journal of Accounting & Finance Review*, 12(1), 35-46.
- Inyada, S.J. (2018). Intellectual capital and bank performance in Nigeria: An empirical analysis using pragmatic models. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 8(2).
- Lawal, L., Lawal, T., & Abdullahi, A. M. (2019). *Intellectual capital efficiency and profitability of listed health care firms in Nigeria*. 5th Annual International Academic Conference Proceedings, Kaduna, Nigeria.
- Lev, B. (2001), *Intangibles: Management, and Reporting*, Brookings Institution Press, Washington, D
- Mahmoud, F. B., Sanni, M., & Aliu, I. D. (2020). Impact of relational capital on performance of public universities in north central Nigeria. *Fountain University Osogbo Journal of Management*, 5(1), 109 - 134.
- Muhammad, A. M. M. (2010). *Impact of corporate governance on intellectual capital efficiency and financial performance*. Published PhD Dissertation, National College of Business Administration and Economics, Lahore.
- Ohidoa, T., & Kolade, A. M. (2024). Executive compensation and firms' financial performance: Analytical approach in Nigeria. *KIU Journal of Social Sciences*, 10(1), 283 – 295.

Michigan International Journal of Corporate Finance and Accounting

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Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MIJCFA>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

Otley, D. T. (2004). *Business performance management: Theory and practice*. Cambridge University Press, UK.

Ozkan, N., Cakan, S., & Kayacan, M. (2017). Intellectual capital and financial performance: A study of the Turkish Banking Sector. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 17(3), 190 – 198.

Rehman, A. U., Aslam, E., & Iqbal, A. (2022). Intellectual capital efficiency and bank performance: Evidence from Islamic banks. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 22(1), 113 – 121. <http://www.elsevier.com/journals/borsa-istanbul-review/2214-8450>

Rastogi, P.N. (2000). Sustaining enterprise competitiveness is human capital the answer. *Human System Management*.19 (3).

Sylvanus, A.N., Okoye, P.V.C., Amahalu, N.N. & Mbonu, C. (2024). Intellectual capital and financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria, *Journal of Global Accounting*, 10(2), 480 - 497. Available:<https://journals.unizik.edu.ng/joga>

Ulum, I., Kharismawati, N., & Syam, D. (2017). Modified value-added intellectual coefficient (MVAIC) and traditional financial performance of Indonesian biggest companies. *International Journal of Learning and Intellectual Capital*, 14(3), 207 – 219.

Xu, J., China, Q., & Liu, F. (2022). Intellectual capital efficiency and firms' financial performance based on business life cycle. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 4(2), 1469 – 1930. DOI 10.1108/JIC-12-2020-0383

Xu, J., & Zhang, Y. (2021). Does intellectual capital measurement matter in financial performance? An investigation of Chinese agricultural listed Companies. *Agronomy*, 11, 1872. <https://doi.org/10.3390/AGRONOMY11091872>

Yousaf, M. (2022). Intellectual capital and firm performance: Evidence from certified firms from the EFQM excellence model. *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*, 33(13-14), 1472 – 1488. DOI: 10.1080/14783363.2021.1972